

MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR SHEEP MEAT

Meat value chain

1. Merino sheep at Finca Las Albaidas, Córdoba 2. Sheep transhumance Las Albaidas, Córdoba 3. Photo caption Locating and monitoring the animals of lasalbaidas.es. Information provided to the final consumer.4. GPS tracking device

THE WHAT AND WHY:

The consumption of sheep meat in Spain is marked by a downward trend in consumption, as it is closely linked to the Christmas holidays and celebrations. The fall in consumption, due to changes in dietary habits or competition in the market with other cheaper meats, has led to the adoption of a strategy to differentiate its production in the case of the "Ganadería las Albaidas", a Merino breed sheep farm located near the city of Córdoba and surrounding areas. This strategy consists of showing the consumer the way in which the lambs, a product of extensive and transhumant livestock farming, have been reared through a QR code, included in the packaging.

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

How to maintain a sustainable livestock system in a peri-urban environment?

The Merino animals are reared in an extensive system, thanks to the use of a wide variety of resources ranging from pastureland, grazing in the mountains, peri-urban pastures, organic olive groves and stubble from the crops of the nearby countryside of Córdoba. This management is possible thanks to the practice of transhumance, which has enabled to increase the consumption of pastures by the herd as opposed to grazing in the stable, offering this difference in meat quality and conferring environmental values such as the maintenance and improvement of one of the "green lungs" of the city, and the increased welfare of the animals that graze freely for most of the year.

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Keywords: Consumption, Merino sheep, meat, value chain, strategy, differentiation, transhumance

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ADVANTAGES

Advantages of differentiation in the sector

The marketing is done through an online platform. The really innovative aspect of this system is in the labelling of the product, which through the application of new technologies for the certification of traceability with blockchain and cattlechain methods, based on GPS technology, has allowed the end consumer to find on the label itself, reliable information about the way the animals are reared, including maps of the grazed areas, the types of fence, the time spent by the mothers in the meadows, images of the grazing in real time... All this, allows to trace the origin and production conditions of sheep meat, thus improving the perception of quality and contributing to customer loyalty.

The traceability certification system, together with direct sales by the producers themselves, allows them to maintain the control of the marketing process right up to the end consumer, being able to incorporate all the environmental values generated in the production process into the value of the product. This system is maintained thanks to the fact that the price of the product in this short channel is more resilient to market fluctuations and represents an increase in the value of the end product compared to that marketed through traditional marketing channels.

The certification of traceability through GPS provides greater knowledge of the product consumed, thus increasing the range of choice. Moreover, from the producer's point of view, it also means diversification of the sales channel.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Online marketing added to the application of new technologies for traceability certification with blockchain and cattlechain methods, based on GPS technology, has allowed the final consumer to find all the information on the label itself.**

- **GPS technology makes it possible to trace the origin and production conditions of sheep meat, thus improving the perception of quality and contributing to customer loyalty.**

- **The practice of transhumance has made it possible to increase the consumption of pasture by the herd as opposed to pasture grazing.**

Livestock from Albaidas farm - transhumance

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